

Constructive Equivalents of the Uniform Continuity Theorem¹

Josef Berger

(Mathematisches Institut, Universität München, Germany
Josef.Berger@mathematik.uni-muenchen.de)

Abstract: For the purpose of constructive reverse mathematics, we show the equivalence of the uniform continuity theorem to a series of propositions; this illuminates the relationship between Brouwer's fan theorem and the uniform continuity theorem.

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Working in the system **EL**, we investigate how the following axioms are related to each other:

- Every pointwise continuous function $F : \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is uniformly continuous.
- Every pointwise continuous function $F : \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is bounded.
- For every pointwise continuous function $F : \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ it is decidable whether it is constant or not.
- The fan theorem: every detachable bar is uniform.

An introduction to the formal system **EL** can be found in Chapter 3 of [7]. Every object is based on natural numbers and functions $\alpha \in \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. There is a canonical bijection between the set $\{0, 1\}^*$ of finite binary sequences and \mathbb{N} , by setting

$$u_0 = (), u_1 = (0), u_2 = (1), u_3 = (00), u_4 = (01), u_5 = (10), u_6 = (11), \dots$$

Therefore, we can work with functions $g \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ as well. A function $\alpha \in \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a binary sequence if

$$\text{bin}(\alpha) \equiv \forall n \in \mathbb{N} (\alpha(n) = 0 \vee \alpha(n) = 1).$$

For any formula A we write

$$\forall \alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} A$$

¹ C. S. Calude, H. Ishihara (eds.). *Constructivity, Computability, and Logic. A Collection of Papers in Honour of the 60th Birthday of Douglas Bridges.*

as an abbreviation of

$$\forall \alpha \in \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \ (bin(\alpha) \rightarrow A).$$

Let $\bar{\alpha}n$ denote the restriction of (finite or infinite) sequences to their first n components. Concatenation of finite sequences u, v is denoted by $u * v$. Finally, let $|u|$ denote the length of a finite binary sequence u . These operations are definable in **EL**. We are interested in continuous functions $F : \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. Under the compact metric

$$d(\alpha, \beta) = \inf \{2^{-n} \mid \bar{\alpha}n = \bar{\beta}n\}$$

on $\{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}}$, pointwise continuity reads as

$$\forall \alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \forall \beta \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} (\bar{\alpha}n = \bar{\beta}n \rightarrow (F(\alpha) = F(\beta))) \quad (1)$$

and uniform continuity reads as

$$\exists n \in \mathbb{N} \forall \alpha, \beta \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} (\bar{\alpha}n = \bar{\beta}n \rightarrow (F(\alpha) = F(\beta))).$$

For the sake of working within **EL**, we use a concept of continuity which is based on functions $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ rather than on functions $F : \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. A function $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ pointwise continuous if

$$pc(f) \equiv \forall \alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(\bar{\alpha}n) = f(\bar{\alpha}n * u)).$$

A function $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is uniformly continuous if

$$uc(f) \equiv \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \forall \alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(\bar{\alpha}n) = f(\bar{\alpha}n * u)).$$

The uniform continuity theorem reads as

$$\mathbf{UC} \equiv \forall f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N} (pc(f) \rightarrow uc(f)).$$

Note that **UC** is equivalent to the statement: each pointwise continuous function $F : \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is uniformly continuous; thus the investigation of the constructive content of the uniform continuity theorem is not biased by representing continuous functions as type 1 objects. For $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ it can be decided whether it is constant or not if

$$dc(f) \equiv \forall u, v \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(u) = f(v)) \vee \exists u, v \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(u) \neq f(v)).$$

Thus we define

$$\mathbf{DC} \equiv \forall f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N} (pc(f) \rightarrow dc(f)).$$

A function $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is bounded if

$$bo(f) \equiv \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(u) \leq n).$$

Let us define

$$\mathbf{PB} \equiv \forall f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N} (pc(f) \rightarrow bo(f)).$$

Now it remains to formalise Brouwer's fan theorem. This is done similarly as in [5]. A function $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a bar if

$$bar(f) \equiv$$

$$\forall u, v \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(u) = 0 \rightarrow f(u * v) = 0) \ \& \ (\forall \alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \exists n (f(\bar{\alpha}n) = 0)).$$

A function $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a uniform bar if

$$ubar(f) \equiv \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \forall \alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} (f(\bar{\alpha}n) = 0).$$

Now we can define

$$\mathbf{FT} \equiv \forall f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N} (bar(f) \rightarrow ubar(f)).$$

For a function $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we define

$$\sup(f, n) \equiv \exists u \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(u) = n) \ \& \ \forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(u) \leq n).$$

Thus $\sup(f, n)$ just says that n is the supremum of f .² Its existence is guaranteed at least in the case of uniform continuity:³

Lemma 1. *EL* $\vdash \forall f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N} (uc(f) \rightarrow \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \sup(f, n))$

Proof. Fix a uniformly continuous f . Then there is $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall \alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}} \forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(\bar{\alpha}m) = f(\bar{\alpha}m * u)).$$

Thus we have

$$\sup(f, \max \{f(u) \mid u \in \{0, 1\}^* \text{ and } |u| \leq m\}).$$

□

At some stage we shall use the following version of the axiom of choice

$$\mathbf{AC}^* \equiv$$

$$\forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (A(u) \vee \neg A(u)) \rightarrow$$

$$\exists g \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N} (\forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (g(u) = 0 \leftrightarrow \neg A(u))),$$

where $A(u)$ is a Σ_1^0 -formula.

² The infimum is treated analogously.

³ See Corollary 4.3 in Chapter 4 of [2] for an informal proof of this fact.

Proposition 2.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{EL} \vdash \mathbf{UC} &\leftrightarrow \mathbf{PB} \\ \mathbf{EL} \vdash \mathbf{UC} &\rightarrow \mathbf{FT} + \mathbf{DC} \\ \mathbf{EL} + \mathbf{AC}^* \vdash \mathbf{FT} + \mathbf{DC} &\rightarrow \mathbf{UC} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. ($\mathbf{EL} \vdash \mathbf{UC} \rightarrow \mathbf{PB}$) This follows from Lemma 1.

($\mathbf{EL} \vdash \mathbf{PB} \rightarrow \mathbf{UC}$) Fix a pointwise continuous $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. We define $g \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ by

$$g(w) = \max(\{k \in \{0, \dots, |w| - 1\} \mid f(\overline{wk}) \neq f(w)\} \cup \{0\})$$

and show that g is pointwise continuous as well. Fix $\alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}}$; there is $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(\overline{\alpha m}) = f(\overline{\alpha m * u})).$$

Fix $u \in \{0, 1\}^*$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} g(\overline{\alpha m}) &= \max(\{k \in \{0, \dots, m - 1\} \mid f(\overline{\alpha k}) \neq f(\overline{\alpha m})\} \cup \{0\}) = \\ &= \max(\{k \in \{0, \dots, m + |u| - 1\} \mid f(\overline{\alpha m * uk}) \neq f(\overline{\alpha m * u})\} \cup \{0\}) = \\ &= g(\overline{\alpha m * u}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus g is pointwise continuous.

Now, by \mathbf{PB} , there is $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (g(u) < k).$$

For every $\alpha \in \{0, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}}$ and for every $u \in \{0, 1\}^*$ we can conclude that

$$f(\overline{\alpha k}) = f(\overline{\alpha k * u}),$$

since otherwise $g(\overline{\alpha k * u}) \geq k$, which is absurd. Thus f is uniformly continuous.

($\mathbf{EL} \vdash \mathbf{UC} \rightarrow \mathbf{FT}$) Let $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ be a bar. Then f is pointwise and therefore uniformly continuous. It follows that f is a uniform bar.

($\mathbf{EL} \vdash \mathbf{UC} \rightarrow \mathbf{DC}$) Let $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ be uniformly continuous. Comparing the supremum of f with the infimum of f yields a decision whether f is constant or not.

($\mathbf{EL} + \mathbf{AC}^* \vdash \mathbf{FT} + \mathbf{DC} \rightarrow \mathbf{UC}$) Fix a pointwise continuous function $f \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. For every $u \in \{0, 1\}^*$ the assignment

$$\{0, 1\}^* \ni w \mapsto u * w$$

is definable in **EL** and pointwise continuous. Thus the function

$$f_u : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}, w \mapsto f(u * w)$$

is pointwise continuous as well. For $u \in \{0, 1\}^*$ we define

$$A(u) \equiv \exists v, w \in \{0, 1\}^* (f(u * v) \neq f(u * w)).$$

Thus $A(u)$ is the Σ_1^0 -statement: f_u is not constant. And $\neg A(u)$ is the statement: f_u is constant. By $dc(f_u)$ we have $A(u) \vee \neg A(u)$. Thus, by **AC*** there is $g \in \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall u \in \{0, 1\}^* (g(u) = 0 \leftrightarrow \neg A(u)).$$

By the definition of A it follows that

$$\forall u, v (g(u) = 0 \rightarrow g(u * v) = 0). \quad (2)$$

By (2) and the pointwise continuity of f we can see that g is a bar; by **FT**, g is a uniform bar, which implies the uniform continuity of f . \square

It was Hajime Ishihara who propagated formal approaches to constructive reverse mathematics [4]. See also the work of Iris Loeb [6] and Wim Veldman [8].

It is well known that in Bishop's constructive mathematics the uniform continuity theorem implies Brouwer's fan theorem. Under continuous choice, the reverse implication holds as well; see Section 3 of Chapter 5 in [3] for proofs of these results. Continuous choice is required in order to assure that pointwise continuous functions possess a modulus of pointwise continuity. That means that the assignment $\forall \alpha \exists n \dots$ in (1) is given by a pointwise continuous function. One can show that Brouwer's fan theorem is equivalent to the proposition: each function which possesses a modulus of pointwise continuity is uniformly continuous [1].

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